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Two new species of Entiminae (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) from Greek Island of Samothrace

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Abstract: *Otiorhynchus fengaricus* sp. n. and *Brachysomus saosensis* sp. n. from North Aegean Sea Island of Samothrace (Greece) are described. Both species show confused morphological characters, as a result they are placed in incertae sedis. *Otiorhynchus beroni* ANGELOV, 1985, *O. georgievi* ANGELOV, 1985, and *O. pavelangelovi* GUÉORGUIEV & MAGNANO, 2007 are transferred from the *Otiorhynchus* subgenus *Podonebistus* to *Otiorhynchus* incertae sedis (all new placement).

Key words: Coleoptera; Curculionidae; taxonomy; new species; *Otiorhynchus*; *Brachysomus*; Greece.

INTRODUCTION

Despite long term entomological research dating back to the 19th century, the fauna of the Greek islands is still poorly known. Even the largest Island of Crete is far from being sufficiently explored as evidenced by the recent descriptions of several new species (the last of them, BIAŁOOKI, 2020) and the lack of a list of the cretan weevils. As concerns entomological research, the North Aegean Sea islands belong to the most neglected areas in Greece; practically nothing is known about weevils of these islands. Recently COLONNELLI (2018, and 2022) described two new species from Island of Thassos. The small Island of Samothrace is the most north-eastern Greek island, apparently never explored by weevil specialists. Short visit to this island in the year 2023 resulted, among other things, in discovery of three new species of weevils representing subfamily Entiminae (snout beetles). Two of them, belonging to the genera *Otiorhynchus* and *Brachysomus* are described below, while the third species from the genus *Parameira* was described separately (BIAŁOOKI 2024).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Body length was measured from the anterior margin of the eyes to the elytral apex. Rostrum length was measured from the anterior margin of the eyes to the anterior part of the epistome. The width of rostrum is defined as the pterygial span, i.e. the distance between the

outer margins of the pterygia. The statement “pterygia projecting” means that pterygia are extending from the outline of the rostrum in dorsal view, whereas “pterygia distant” denotes condition in which the anterior margin of the pterygia are clearly located behind the anterior margin of the rostrum between the mandibles and the pterygia. Various areas of legs, dorsal and ventral margins in particular, are described as if legs were stretched horizontally at right angle to longitudinal body axis, what allows for a precise terminology. Modified insertions of setae along ventral wall of tibiae forming usually pointed tubercles are hereby termed (tibial) spines. Enlarged terminal (proximal) end of the spiculum ventrale is named caput in the text. Although aedeagus is defined, as generally accepted, as pedon with apodemes, the two terms i.e. aedeagus and pedon are used interchangeably, depending on the context, particularly while taking measurements. The same approach applies to the female 8th sternite, therefore terms such as “plate/lamella of 8th sternite” are rejected. “/” separates label data of different specimens. Since the border between frons and epifrons is completely unclear in large majority of species, I still prefer to apply more general term “dorsal wall of rostrum” (= frons + epifrons). Length of funicle segments is taken without basal condyle.

Dissected terminalia of both sexes are stored in a microvial with glycerine pinned under the card bearing the specimen (occasionally, damaged parts are glued to this card).

The photographs were taken with JVC KYF75 digital camera attached to Leica M205C stereomicroscope and stacked using the AutoMontage software by Syncroscopy.

Acronyms: BIAL – collection of P.Z. Białooki, Sopot, Poland; KAKI – collection of George Kakiopoulos, Athens, Greece; USMB – collection of the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom, Poland; WANA – collection of Marek Wanat, Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław, Poland. Holotype is abbreviated as “ht”.

RESULTS

Subfamily Entiminae SCHOENHERR, 1823

Tribe Otiorhynchini SCHOENHERR, 1826

Genus *Otiorhynchus* GERMAR, 1822 (type species *Otiorhynchus rhacusensis* GERMAR, 1822).

***Otiorhynchus* (incertae sedis) *fengaricus* sp. n.**

<https://zoobank.org/NomenclaturalActs/539EC58A-5FBA-40B1-848D-F18BCCD0CC4C>

(Figs. 1–6)

Material examined: holotype male dissected: 01.06.2023 NE Greece, Samothrace Island, S Therma, 400 m [BIAL]. Paratypes: as ht, 5 exx. \ same label, but 31.05.2023, 1 ex. [BIAL; USMB; WANA].

Diagnosis. *Otiorhynchus fengaricus* sp. n. belongs to the small group of the three hitherto known blind species from Bulgaria. All of them are now placed (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023) in the subgenus *Podonebistus* REITTER, 1913 what is obviously incorrect due to disparate outer morphology as well as terminalia of both sexes. Probably, they were placed in *Podonebistus* solely because of their narrowly elongate elytra. Since the previous placement in *Troglorhynchus* was similarly erroneous, in the absence of a well resolved systematic position, I prefer to place species of this group in *Otiorhynchus* incertae sedis. The new species differs instantly from all the three hitherto known species from Bulgaria in significantly larger body; relatively well-developed, although markedly reduced eyes; evidently elongate prothorax; and fairly long, moderately strongly raised, nearly semi-erect

elongate elytral scales. It moreover differs from *O. (incertae sedis) beroni* ANGELOV, 1985 (**new placement**) in small, yet well-developed teeth on all femora, and shape of aedeagus (distinctly excised apically in *fengaricus* while rounded in *beroni*); from *O. (incertae sedis) gueorgievi* ANGELOV, 1985 (**new placement**) in tooth of profemur much smaller; and from *O. (incertae sedis) pavelangelovi* GUÉORGUIEV & MAGNANO, 2007 (**new placement**) in male metatibia stronger downcurved, distally narrowly tapering; ventral margin with larger, broadly obtuse tubercles. All the three species are hereby transferred from *Otiorhynchus (Podonebistus)* to *Otiorhynchus (incertae sedis)*.

Description. Male: Size range 5.8-6.4 mm; ht 6.4 mm; body bright brown to moderately dark brown; devoid of broad recumbent scales, covered with long seta-like scales (Fig. 1), only ventral part of rostrum with dense elongate recumbent scales.

Mandibles small yet well visible from above, outer margins slightly angulate.

Rostrum (Fig. 1) relatively strongly elongate, almost $1.3 \times$ longer than broad, not separated from head dorsally; pterygia fairly weakly yet distinctly distant, large, strongly projecting; ventral and lateral walls of rostrum between scrobes and eyes covered with elongate yet fairly broad bright brown recumbent dense scales completely obscuring surface; epistome shortly triangular, very shallowly hollowed, covered with similar irregular rugosity as rest of dorsal wall of rostrum which is gradually confluent with head; median sulcus well-developed, moderately deep, with fairly well defined margins, covered with sparse, short, narrow, elongate, bright brown recumbent scales.

Head short, fairly strongly transverse but nevertheless rather narrow, moderately strongly, rectilinearly tapering, forming common cone with basal part of rostrum; nearly $1.6 \times$ broader than rostrum minimum width; interocular area fairly strongly convex transversally due to minute (0.3 interocular distance) hardly convex, distinctly elongate eyes tangential to dorsal outline of head, when viewed from above; temples moderately strongly tapering, distinctly longer than longest eye diameter; median fovea not recognizable, fused with median sulcus of dorsal wall of rostrum reaching backwards behind hind margins of eyes; scales similar to those on rostrum but distinctly longer, directed transversally towards body axis; gular suture well-developed; ventral wall of head with irregularly shaped dense furrows, shiny.

Antennae long and slender; scape $1.05 \times$ shorter than funicle, distinctly s-shaped (in dorsal view), subparallel-sided, only short distal part weakly widened; covered with large, very dense elongate punctures and weakly raised bright brown, fairly long, narrow elongate scales, visibly stronger raised along anterior margin; first funicle segment ca. $2.6 \times$ longer than wide and $1.15 \times$ longer than second, which is indistinctly narrower and slightly less elongate ($2.55 \times$); segments 3-7 subequally long and wide, ca. $1.2-1.4 \times$ longer than broad; condyles fairly short but well-developed; each segment of 3-7 with irregular two combs of bright brown moderately long almost straight semi-erect setae; club large, $2.3 \times$ longer than broad; basally extremely strongly pedunculate (width of basal long part ca. one third club width, slightly yet distinctly narrower than funicle segments).

Prothorax $1.1 \times$ longer than broad; anterior margin and base subequally long; widest indistinctly before middle, concavely tapering towards base, as a result very short basal part subparallel-sided; longitudinally moderately evenly convex; disc covered with large dense pit-like circular punctures; interspaces distinctly narrower than punctures diameter, flat, shiny, with very sparsely irregularly distributed small punctures; latero-ventral walls with pit-like punctures somewhat larger, somewhat irregularly shaped, shallower; interspaces very narrow, slightly microsculptured; disc covered with sparse narrow raised scales much longer than on head, directed to center; impunctate area not developed.

Elytra 1.65 × longer than broad, ovate, broadest in basal quarter, moderately strongly tapering backwards, apex narrowly rounded; longitudinally flat (Fig. 2); declivity moderately convex, vertical; striae composed of fairly large, fairly deep well delimited subisodiametric pit-like punctures with submicroscopic weakly perceptible horizontal hair on anterior wall; interpaces somewhat shorter than punctures diameter, flat shiny, devoid of vestiture; interstices as wide as striae to slightly broader on disc, with moderately large weakly rasp-like punctures bearing long (somewhat longer than width of interstices) weakly bowed, parallel-sided ca. 10 × longer than broad, bright brown almost semi-erect scales.

Exposed part of scutellum minute but well visible, triangular; metaventrite covered with moderately large fairly shallow yet well delimited dense punctures; interspaces somewhat convex, covered with moderately developed microsculpture; vestiture consisting of scales similar to raised elytral scales, but less erected; mesoventral process very weakly convex longitudinally, narrow slightly exceeding 0.2 mesocoxa diameter; metaventrite very long, 0.8 first ventrite; metanepisternal suture almost totally reduced, only trace of its anterior part retained (very close to margin of elytra thus weakly perceptible).

Legs moderately long, fairly slender excepting hind tibiae; femora relatively weakly clavate, covered with fairly weakly raised long bright setae; profemur with small but well-developed wide obtuse tooth; middle femur with similar tooth; hind femur with much larger, distally fairly broadly rounded tooth; tibiae covered with semierect fairly long bright setae; all corbels with well-developed inner flange; long red-bright brown mucro on all tibiae; protibiae slender, dorsal margin straight, distal half slightly downcurved; ventral margin devoid of spines; protibia subparallel-sided in lateral view except for short narrow basal intersection and somewhat broadened distal part; apical comb consisting of long, dense, narrow, yellowish bright brown setae; mesotibiae much shorter, distally stronger obliquely extended ventrad; hind tibiae (Fig. 3) short and fairly robust, strongly downcurved; ventral margin with several large obtuse tubercle-like spines, largest spine close to knee, somewhat flattened laterally, semitransparent red-bright brown, brighter than tibia; semi-erect setae on ventral wall somewhat longer than on dorsal wall; tibial spurs not developed; tarsi moderately slender; second tarsite subisodiametric; third segment much broader than preceding tarsite, consisting of two fairly narrow lobes; onychium slender, weakly, gradually widened distally, its projecting portion distinctly shorter than length of third segment.

First ventrite indistinctly, shallowly impressed, irregularly rugoso-punctate; ventrites 2-4 sparsely punctate; metacoxal process 0.5 first ventrite width, its anterior margin slightly v-shaped, mesally extended forwards; last ventrite 1.6 × broader than long, distally very broadly rounded; evenly weakly convex, covered with moderately large, moderately dense punctures, replaced by minute, well developed, moderately dense tubercles (interspaces subequal to tubercles diameter) on fairly large distal area; all ventrites covered with long moderately sparse bright brown hair-like subsemierect scales.

Aedeagus (Fig. 5) with pedon weakly arched, 2.2 × longer than broad, 1.6 × shorter than apodemes; subparallel-sided, widest basally and subapically; tegminal ring very narrow; parameres short, subequally long as width of pedon, narrowly (ca. one quarter of pedon width) separated from each other, moderately diverging, narrow, subparallel-sided; projecting part of endophallus subequally long as pedon length; transfer apparatus well sclerotized and pigmented, fairly large and complex.

Sexual dimorphism rather inconspicuous; female differs from male in somewhat broader, less elongate, more evidently ovate elytra; metatibiae straight, ventral wall with very small inconspicuous spines (Fig. 4); first ventrite flat; last ventrite punctate throughout, indistinctly narrower rounded distally, shallowly yet markedly impressed subapically.

Female 8th sternite subisodiametric; distally deeply excised, resulting in two lobes with protruding hairs along their distal margins; arms straight, fairly long, diverging at angle somewhat less than 45 degree; spiculum ventrale ca. 2.5 × longer than sternite, caput minute; ovipositor short, ca. twice as short as spiculum ventrale, coxites moderately broadly separated basally, distinctly converging to each other distally, weakly sclerotized, moderately pigmented; styli small, subisodiametric, with several long protruding hairs; vagina diverging gradually towards bursa creating uniform structure ca. 4.5 × longer and 3 × broader than ovipositor; entry of common oviduct in basal one thirds of this composite structure; spermatheca (Fig. 6) with cornu long, moderately arched, gradually tapering towards apex, moderately deviating from corpus; corpus visibly thicker than cornu, markedly bowed; nodulus minute, slightly curved towards ramus which is subisodiametric, distinctly larger than nodulus.

Ecology. All specimens were sifted from ground litter consisting largely of dead oak leaves at altitude ca. 400 m on northern slopes of Mount Fengari.

Distribution. Known only from locus typicus, most probably endemic to the Island of Samothrace.

Etymology. Specific epithet patronymic, after Mount Fengari, the highest summit of the Saos range on the Island of Samothrace.

Tribe Sciaphilini SHARP, 1891 (type genus *Sciaphilus* SCHOENHERR, 1823)

Genus *Brachysomus* SCHOENHERR, 1823 (type species *Curculio echinatus* BONSDORFF, 1785).

Brachysomus (incertae sedis) ***saosensis*** sp. n.

<https://zoobank.org/NomenclaturalActs/5BD422CA-F165-496E-BD87-7BB93850E384>

(Figs. 7–12)

Material examined: holotype male, dissected [hind left onychium missing]: 31.05.2023 NE Greece, Samothrace Island, S Therma, 400 m [BIAL]. Paratypes: as ht, 5 exx. \ 01.06.2023 same label, 33 exx. [BIAL; KAKI; USMB; WANA].

Diagnosis. This is only the second example of island endemism in the large genus *Brachysomus* consisting hitherto of almost sixty species. The first one is represented by *B. samos* (YUNAKOV & GERMANN, 2022), interestingly, also on Aegean island. The systematic position of *Brachysomus saosensis* sp. n. is unclear due to confused certain significant morphological characters, first of all presence of well-developed, long parameres typical of *Brachysomus* s. str. I place the new species in *Brachysomus* incertae sedis due to no trace of head constriction behind eyes (what seems to exclude the new species from *Amicromias*, species of which have long parameres, but the new species could well be *Amicromias* with reduced head constriction). Scrobes are identical as in *Hippomias* i.e. both dorsal and ventral margins are obsolete behind antennal fossa but well-developed parameres rather do not allow for the placement in this subgenus. Further adding to the confusion, the new species can not be unequivocally assigned to any species group (only preliminarily established and poorly defined) when using the key in YUNAKOV 2022, since elytral recumbent scales are predominantly neither round nor elliptic but elongate drop-shaped, broadest subbasally and tapering distally into long narrow pointed apex. Also a new species of *Brachysomus* (GERMANN & BIALOOKI [in press]) is difficult to be satisfactorily placed for the same reason: well-developed parameres accompanied by reduced scrobes. Generally, systematics of *Brachysomus* and related/similar genera discussed by YUNAKOV 2022 is still far from

being satisfactorily resolved. Surprisingly, YUNAKOV l.c. did not discuss the two groups now recognized as distinct genera that in my opinion are most close to *Brachysomus* i.e. *Myiacomorphus* SOLARI, 1948 and *Pseudoptochus* FORMÁNEK, 1905. The status of these two genera, as well as *Amicromias*, and their relationship to the genus *Brachysomus* needs to be thoroughly reconsidered, what is well beyond the scope of this paper. The new species is similar to *Brachysomus samos* in having identical scaling pattern on elytra, and body coloration. However, it is very different from that species due to several highly significant characters: pedon much longer in comparison to apodemes; parameres well-developed; disparate endophallic structures; different spermatheca; elytral recumbent scales smaller and darker (as a result general body color darker), not excised apically, narrowly tapering; single rows of scales on interstices consisting of much shorter, less raised, visible only in profile, strongly arched scales; meso- and metaventrite with sparse vestiture, not contrasting with remaining parts of ventral side of thorax and abdomen; rostrum shorter, unambiguously transverse; first funicle segment much longer than second, slightly shorter than segments 2+3 combined; funicle segments 3-7 strongly transverse; elytra much less elongate, what suggests that the two species not necessarily are closely related.

Description. Male: Size range 2.1-3.0 mm (ht 2.2 mm); body brown, legs and antennae fairly bright red-brown; scales bright- and dark brown.

Mandibles weakly visible from above; their outer margins with hardly perceptible trace of pedicel of mandibular process.

Rostrum evidently transverse, 0.85 pterygial span; basally tapering towards antennal insertions, distally parallel-sided.

Dorsal wall of rostrum distinctly convex longitudinally, at angle to interocular area; mesally ended slightly behind anterior margins of eyes, lateral part ended distinctly before eyes; covered with minute dense punctures and very short, moderately dense, semi-erect, strongly arched, elongate (several times longer than broad), moderately wide scales directed forward and slightly outwards; along median sulcus and anteriorly to antennal insertions scales hair-like; median sulcus narrow and shallow yet well visible; epistome obsolete, not impressed, lateral keels not developed; scrobes fully visible from above, pit-like, without pronounced both ventral and dorsal margins.

Head strongly transverse, weakly tapering; temples somewhat shorter than eye diameter, distinctly rounded; eyes distinctly elongate, moderately strongly convex, distinctly projecting, small, longest diameter ca. 0.4 interocular distance; interocular area sharply delimited from dorsal wall of rostrum due to scales visibly longer and broader; ventral wall of head devoid of conspicuous sculpture and vestiture, apparently bare, shiny, sharply contrasting with dorsal part of head.

Antennae moderately robust; scape fairly slender, gradually weakly broadened, somewhat s-shaped; covered with minute dense punctures and short weakly raised hair-like scales; funicle robust, first segment $1.8 \times$ longer than wide ca. $1.4 \times$ longer than second, which is less elongate ($1.4 \times$ longer than wide) and distinctly narrower than first; segments 3-7 gradually stronger transverse; club ovate, basally broadly rounded, apically moderately tapering, $1.65 \times$ longer than broad, as long as four distal funicle segments combined, visibly broader than scape.

Prothorax moderately strongly transverse, $1.3 \times$ broader than long, laterally moderately rounded, widest in middle; longitudinally very weakly, evenly convex; disc covered with extremely small, dense irregularly shaped and sized shiny tubercles; vestiture consisting of

(sub)recumbent elongate moderately dense greyish bright brown scales; latero-ventral walls covered with larger and less shiny tubercles, scales slightly darker.

Elytra very shortly ovate, merely $1.2 \times$ longer than broad, $2.55 \times$ longer, and $1.6 \times$ broader than prothorax; basally very strongly arched, only slightly less so distally; widest somewhat before middle; longitudinally fairly weakly, evenly convex, declivity moderately overhanging; striae shallowly yet clearly impressed; each strial puncture with single submicroscopic, hardly perceptible hair; interstices flat ca. $3 \times$ broader than striae, covered with very short (ca. $5 \times$ shorter than width of interstice) moderately dense recumbent, elongate $4\text{--}5 \times$ longer than wide scales broadest subbasally, arcuately tapering, pointed distally to subparallel-sided; scales creating more or less visible darker pattern resembling that in e.g. *Brachysomus samos*; along interstices single irregular row of fairly weakly raised, strongly arcuate, oval spatulate scales somewhat longer than recumbent.

Legs fairly short, covered with narrow, elongate, recumbent to somewhat raised, variously elongate (hair-like to ca. $4 \times$ longer than wide) arcuate bright scales; femora fairly bright red-brown with darker knee; tibiae fairly robust, with short weakly perceptible mucro; distal comb consisting of dense long narrow bright setae; dorsal margin of pro- and mesotibiae straight, very short distal intersection hardly upcurved; hind tibiae distinctly sabre-shaped (upcurved apically); tarsi very robust, second tarsite strongly transverse; onychium narrow, very weakly widened apically, its projecting part visibly shorter than preceding tarsite.

Ventrites covered with small, moderately dense punctures, interspaces uneven, in part convex, and with short weakly raised bright hair-like scales; first two ventrites very shallowly impressed; last ventrite $2.25 \times$ broader than long, covered with small rasp-like punctures, distally moderately narrowly rounded, with hardly recognizable apical impression covered with bunch of sparse, markedly longer scales.

Aedeagus well sclerotized, $2.6 \times$ longer than broad, $1.6 \times$ shorter than apodemes; basal half subparallel-sided, apex fairly strongly tapering, pointed; weakly arched, basally somewhat stronger so; parameres well-developed, basal 0.4 broadly connate, distal part weakly diverging; endophallus inside pedon without any conspicuous structures except for subapical lobes; its distal part (ca. two thirds) outside pedon with complex irregular fields of microsclerites; transfer apparatus small, irregularly Y-shaped.

Sexual dimorphism normal for *Brachysomus* and *Amicromias*; female differs from male in on average larger body; elytra larger, slightly more elongate, $1.25 \times$ longer than broad, much larger in comparison to prothorax: almost $2.95 \times$ longer and $1.7 \times$ broader; declivity somewhat stronger overhanging; first ventrite convex; last ventrite more narrowly tapering, distally narrower rounded.

Female 8th sternite indistinctly elongate, with axial dark pigmentation; spiculum ventrale devoid of caput; ovipositor somewhat longer than 8th sternite, weakly pigmented; vagina somewhat shorter than spiculum ventrale, as wide as ovipositor base, with characteristic transverse corrugation, markedly less pigmented than ovipositor; bursa somewhat shorter than vagina, colorless, basally very narrow, apically gradually widened; spermatheca with short, fairly strongly deviating cornu; ramus very large, distinctly elongate; nodulus very short.

Ecology. All specimens collected together with *Otiorhynchus fengaricus* **sp. n.**

Distribution. *Brachysomus saosensis* **sp. n.** is only known from locus typicus, and most probably is endemic to the North Aegean Island of Samothrace.

Etymology. Specific epithet (adjective) is patronymic, after Saos Mountains.

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Fig. 1. *Otiorhynchus fengaricus* sp. n., male.

Fig. 2. *Otiorhynchus fengaricus* sp. n., male profile.

Fig. 3. *Otiorhynchus fengaricus* sp. n., male metatibia.

Fig. 4. *Otiorhynchus fengaricus* sp. n., female metatibia.

Fig. 5. *Otiorhynchus fengaricus* sp. n., aedeagus dorsal view.

Fig. 6. *Otiorynchus fengaricus* sp. n., spermatheca.

Fig. 7. *Brachysomus saosensis* sp. n., male.

Fig. 8. *Brachysomus saosensis* sp. n., female.

Fig. 9. *Brachysomus saosensis* sp. n., female profile.

Fig. 10. *Brachysomus saosensis* sp. n., aedeagus dorsal view.

Fig. 11. *Brachysomus saosensis* sp. n., aedeagus profile.

Fig. 12. *Brachysomus saosensis* sp. n., spermatheca.

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